

Interaction of Laser Diffraction Intensity Through High Voltage Plasma Interaction: An Experimental Study

-Ayush Gupta

Abstract

This experiment investigates the effect of plasma generated at a single slit on the interference pattern of a laser beam. Using a 532nm class 3 laser we directed it to a slit connected to a high-voltage power supply of 3K Volts creating a plasma discharge at the slit. The interference patterns were recorded and analysed both with and without the plasma present. The results indicated a very slight deflection in the intensity of fringes when plasma was introduced. This tells us that the presence of ionized gas alters the refractive index in the region of the slit. This may be due to the fact that plasma might be inducing oscillations or disturbances within the laser's interaction zone. The findings provide insight into the interaction between plasma and when light is diffracting.

Introduction

The Laser-plasma interactions particularly the phenomenon of self-focusing have been studied earlier but this study has been more focused in the interaction between the diffraction pattern, laser and plasma behaviour. The phenomenon of interference patterns is a fundamental demonstration of the wave nature of light, first shown by Young's double-slit experiment but to avoid complexity we will be using a single slit. When light by a laser passes through a single slit, it creates a distinct pattern of alternating bright and dark fringes due to constructive and destructive interference. In this experiment we aim to explore that what would be happen if we introduce Plasma into the experimental setup. Plasma is often called as the fourth state of matter that is created when gas is ionized through the use of high voltage

resulting in a collection of charged particles that can influence the behaviour of light.

By generating plasma exactly at the point where the laser beam passes through the slit. We are making a simple hypothesis that the diffraction pattern will get a little bit of distorted or fluctuated or the change in intensity of the pattern due to changes in the refractive index at the point where we are making plasma caused by the presence of ionized gas. This research tries to see the interaction between Plasma and light when light is diffracting.

Methodology

1.Experimental Setup

The experiment was designed to measure the change in laser intensity when it was diffracting through the single slit while passing through plasma. We are using an LDR (Light Dependent Resistor) and a solar panel connected to the Analog pins of an Arduino Nano for detection. The following components were used:

- **Laser:** A 532 nm green laser with <1000 mW output was used as the light source and slit was made with blades from pencil sharpener.
- **Plasma Generator:** A high-voltage circuit from a mosquito racket was modified to generate plasma between the slit. The high-voltage circuit had a stable DC source.
- **Sensors:** A light-dependent resistor (LDR) was placed at the central maxima of the diffraction pattern and a small solar panel were placed beside the LDR with other small fringes. They were placed at a distance of 225 cm from the slit to measure the intensity and see any distortion of pattern of the light before and after interaction with the plasma.

- **Arduino Board:** An Arduino Nano was used to interface the sensors with a computer for data logging and processing.
- **FFT Analysis:** Data from the solar panel and LDR were captured and a Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) was applied to analyse the frequency components of the laser signal using MATLAB.

2. Procedure

The following steps were performed:

- **Environment:** The lights of the room were turned off so that it does not contaminate the readings.
- **Sensor Baseline Measurement:** The sensor was taped to the wall to see how much intensity of environmental noise was present. Also, the high voltage plasma was turned on to see if the light from the plasma was interfering with the data from the LDR and the Solar Panel but it was not interfering.

The LDR and the Solar Panel

- Sensor Measurement with laser:** The laser was passed through a single slit to the LDR present at central maxima and the solar panel present besides the LDR without the plasma and the intensity was measured using the LDR and the solar panel. This provided the baseline intensity of the laser light.

The Single Slit Diffraction Pattern

The Diffraction Pattern on Sensors

The Laser and Single Slit Setup

- Plasma Activation:** The high-voltage circuit was activated so it was generating plasma between the two blades at the exact point

where the laser was diffracting. The laser was then passed through the plasma and the intensity change in intensity was captured. The readings from both the LDR and the solar panel were recorded simultaneously.

High voltage plasma on the Single Slit

- **Fourier Transform Analysis:** The data collected from the solar panel and LDR were processed using MATLAB. An FFT was performed to see any frequency shifts or modulations in the light caused by the plasma.

Result/Discussion

There were no visual changes like distortion observed in the diffraction pattern due to the introduction of plasma. The intensity of the laser on the central maxima was increased by 5 to 6 units with the

help of plasma. Specifically with the Fast Fourier Analysis of the LDR sensor the frequency components in the lower range (1–5 Hz) became more noticeable with the peak magnitude increasing from approximately 3500 units to 4800 units. This tells us that the plasma is influencing the intensity and distribution of frequencies within the laser's electromagnetic field. The modulation/fluctuations observed could be due to the self-focusing effect of the plasma, causing an amplification of the beam's intensity. The self-focusing effect here could be due to the addition of refractive index of plasma to the air around the slit. Moreover, the introduction of new frequency components (in the range of 5–10 Hz) indicates that the plasma might be inducing oscillations or disturbances within the laser's interaction zone.

Figure 1: Illustration of how refractive index affects the focusing of light rays.

Source - https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Refractive_index

This amplification effect, likely due to plasma-induced modulation. It could open up new path for controlling laser beams in many experimental setups. Further studies on the interaction mechanisms

between laser light and plasma including electric field measurements and temperature variations are necessary to fully understand the dynamics at play.

Acknowledgement

The experiments and analysis conducted in this paper were performed using tools such as MATLAB for data processing and Arduino for data acquisition from the sensors. I would like to acknowledge the official documentation and tutorials from YouTube and Google of these platforms for providing the necessary technical details for the setup and execution of the experiments.

Citations

- [Plasma \(physics\) - Wikipedia](#)
- [A review on self focusing in laser plasma interaction - ScienceDirect](#)
- [Understanding the Discrete Fourier Transform and the FFT \(youtube.com\)](#)
- [Self-focusing - Wikipedia](#)